

Conditions for the Potentiometric Titration of Copper with Sodium Sulphide and a Use of Platinum Electrode.

BY JANG BAHADUR JHA.

Owing to the extremely low solubility of many metallic sulphides, their potentiometric titration with sodium sulphide attracted an early attention. During these titrations, mercury was chosen as an indicator electrode because reversible electrodes for a large number of metals are difficult to prepare. The working of the mercury electrode is simple. Mercury ions which are sent into the solution combine with the sulphide ions forming sparingly soluble mercury sulphide. The concentration of Hg^{++} and consequently the electrode potential is solely determined by the relation

Thus the mercury electrode acts as an indicator for the sulphide ions.

Using the above electrode Pinkhof (*Dissert. Amsterdam, 1919*) and other workers titrated many metals with sodium sulphide but the results were in general unsatisfactory. Even the compensation electrode method devised by Pinkhof failed to give satisfactory results. Thus when copper was titrated in presence of dilute sulphuric acid with silver in 0.5N-NaCl as compensation electrode the error amounted to 10%; subsequently when the titration was carried on in presence of a bicarbonate and tartaric acid the error reduced to 3%. The failure to obtain more accurate results has been attributed to the peculiar nature of the sulphides and to the great adsorption that takes place during their precipitation (Kolthof and Furman, "Potentiometric Titrations," 1926, p. 193).

It was accidentally found that a plain platinum wire could be used as an indicator electrode in place of the mercury electrode described above, in titrations with sodium sulphide. Consequently a platinum wire of 3 mm. diameter was used throughout the titrations given below.

But the chief reason for the large percentage of error and inconsistent results was found to be the presence of free mineral acids which were added to the metallic salt solutions. Even the presence of acetic acid has a considerable effect on the results. In an experiment varying amounts of a 0.38N-acetic acid were added into several beakers each containing 25 c.c. of copper sulphate solution (0.01527 g. of copper per 25 c.c.), and then titrated with standardised sodium sulphide solution. It was found that the amount of the reagent required to reach the end point increased with the amount of the acetic acid. The results are given in Table I.

TABLE I.

Acetic acid (c.c.)	...	0	1	2	3	4	5
Na ₂ S required (c.c.)	...	27.67	27.94	28.18	28.29	28.41	28.56
Deviation from the calc. vol. of the sulphide (%)	...	-0.8	-0.1	+0.7	+1.1	+1.6	+2.0

The strength of the sodium sulphide solution was determined by the Treadwell and Myr's method (*Z. anorg. Chem.*, 1915, 92, 127).

The results have been plotted in Fig. 1 from which it is seen that the error increases almost linearly with the amount of the free acid

and it is least when 1 c.c. of the acid was present in 25 c.c. of the copper sulphate solution. The presence of sodium acetate is favourable for the estimation.

In practice it has been found that the proportion of the acetic acid to that of copper can be varied within certain limits. For solutions containing up to 12 g. of copper sulphate per litre, 1 c.c. of about 0.4N-acetic acid per 25 c.c. of the solution gives results with least error. For solutions of higher concentrations, greater amounts of acetic acid are necessary.

Another point which deserves attention is that the sodium sulphide which is used as the precipitating reagent in these titrations is rarely available in a pure state; it more often contains varying amounts of sulphite which reacts on the hydrogen sulphide and thus introduces a positive error. Even the best qualities available are not free from it. Freshly prepared sodium sulphide according to Böttger's directions has been found satisfactory (Böttger, *Annalen*, 1884, 223, 335) and the solutions can be prepared by weighing the requisite quantity and dissolving it in the necessary volume of freshly prepared distilled water and then standardised. In order to preserve the strength of sodium sulphide solution it was found necessary to keep it under hydrogen. An arrangement similar to that used for titrations with titanous salts was used (Knecht and Hibbert, "New Reduction Methods in Volumetric Analysis", 1925, p. 63). The sodium sulphide solutions show a certain change in their strength during first 48 hours even under hydrogen after which period they have been found to retain their strength at least for 3 weeks. The standardisation should be done after this period.

Standardisation of sodium sulphide solution was done by direct titration with a copper sulphate solution containing a known amount of copper, although Treadwell and Myr's method may be used. A weighed piece of analytical copper was dissolved in dilute sulphuric acid containing a few c.c. of nitric acid. After warming to drive off nitric acid and its fumes the contents were diluted and the excess of the acid neutralised with caustic soda solution till a permanent green precipitate was obtained. Proper amount of the acetic acid was then added and the solution made up to a known volume. It was then titrated with the sodium sulphide solution to be standardised.

The method has been tested by making a large number of titrations with copper sulphate solutions of different strengths. The

potential attends steadiness soon after adding the reagent and shaking. The abrupt change at the end point is well marked. The copper sulphate solutions for titrations were prepared either from copper sulphate A.R. (B.D.H.) or from copper foil. The results of gravimetric and electroanalytical methods (Sand, *J. Chem. Soc.*, 1907, 41, 63) were taken to represent the actual amount of copper in the solution. Some of the results of titrations are given in Table II.

TABLE II.

Found Cu in 25 c.c. of the sol.	Actual Cu in 25 c.c.	Error.	Found Cu in 25 c.c. of the sol.	Actual Cu in 25 c.c.	Error.
0.3016 g.	0.3018 g.	-0.06%	0.09435 g.	0.09415 g.	+0.06 %
0.2626	0.2623	+0.1	0.01528	0.01527	+0.2
0.1990	0.1985	+0.2	0.007125	0.007095	+0.4
0.1518	0.1516	+0.1	0.005592	0.005580	+0.2
0.1154	0.1152	+0.2	0.005385	0.005345	+0.7

The above figures show that for solutions up to $M/100$ dilution (approximately) the maximum error is 0.2 %, it however increases on further dilution. The error is most likely due to the presence of oxygen in distilled water. It is also significant to note that the error is in every case positive except the first one. If the solutions be made in distilled water free from dissolved gases, and the titrations carried on in an atmosphere of nitrogen, the error is likely to be eliminated or further reduced.

The characteristic titration curve is shown in Fig 2. It is to be observed that the potentials after the inflexion become unsteady and further prolongation of the curve was found to be impossible. But this is no hindrance in locating the end point.

The use of the platinum electrode in such titrations lacks theoretical foundation. The only other instance of this kind where Pt-electrode has been used, is for titration of silver nitrate with alkali halides (*cf.* Müller, *Z. Elektrochem.*, 1924, 30, 419). As an explanation, it has been assumed that the wire becomes coated with the metal during the titration (Kolthof and Furman, *ibid.*, p. 102). It is expected that further work will show that in titrations with sodium sulphide the potential of the platinum wire is due jointly to the concentrations of H^+ and S^{2-} ions. The observed unsteadiness will then be ascribed to the escaping of the hydrogen sulphide after all the metal has been precipitated.

SUMMARY.

1. The effect of free acetic acid in the titrations of copper sulphate with sodium sulphide has been studied.

2. It is shown that by regulating the amount of free acetic acid, copper can be titrated potentiometrically with a platinum electrode.

3. The view is suggested that the potential at the platinum electrode in the above case depends on the activities of hydrogen and sulphur ions.

CHEMICAL LABORATORIES,
AGRA COLLEGE,
AGRA, INDIA.

Received August 7, 1933.

